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Regulation of cellular metabolism by NOD2.

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Regulation of cellular metabolism by NOD2 occurred through control of succinate dehydrogenase (*SDH*) and isocitrate dehydrogenase (*IDH*) isoforms, glycerol kinase (*GK*), hexokinase 2 (*HK2*), malic enzyme 3 (*ME3*), and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (*G6PD*).